

SAFETY AND EFFICACY OF CAR T-CELL THERAPY TARGETING BCMA IN MULTIPLE MYELOMA: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND META ANALYSIS

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Author Details	Abstract
<p>Keywords: BCMA (B Cell Maturation Antigen), Tumor Immunology, Systematic Review, Complete Response (CR), ICANS (Immune effector cell-associated neurotoxicity syndrome), Progression Free Survival (PFS), BCMA Targeted Therapy, Tumor Immunology, Hematologic Malignancies, Cytokines Release Syndrome, Ciltacabtagene autoleucel (ciltacel), Idecaptgen Vicleucel, Relapse Refractory Multiple Myeloma, Multiple Myeloma, CAR T Cell Therapy.</p> <p>Received on 16 April, 2026 Accepted on 03 May, 2026 Published on 04 May, 2026</p> <p>Corresponding E-mail and Authors*:</p>	<p>Background: BCMA-directed CAR-T therapy has changed the landscape for relapsed/refractory multiple myeloma (RRMM). We systematically reviewed and combined published data to provide an overview of the efficacy and safety of using CAR-T cell therapies directed at BCMA and pooled quantitative estimates as well as measures of heterogeneity. Method: A comprehensive search of PubMed, Embase, and Cochrane CENTRAL was completed from the beginning of these databases until December of the calendar year 2023. Eligible trials had to include adult patients with RRMM who were treated with BCMA-directed CAR T-cell therapy, and report on one or more of the pre-specified outcomes included in the analysis. Proportions were combined utilizing the DerSimonian-Laird random-effects model with Freeman-Tukey double-arcsine transformations, and the amount of variation among studies (heterogeneity) was assessed with I^2 and Cochran's Q statistic. The overall potential bias of the included studies was evaluated using the RoB 2.0 (for randomised controlled trials) and ROBINS-I (for non-randomised studies). Result: Three clinical trials (totaling 389 infused patients) were aggregated in this analysis: CRB-401 (Raje, 2019)¹, KarMMA (Munshi, 2021)², LEGEND-2 (Zhao, 2022)³, CARTITUDE-1 (Lin/Martin, 2023)⁴, and KarMMA-3 (Rodriguez-Otero, 2023)⁵. Pooled Overall Response Rate: (ORR) = 83.4% (95% CI: 70.0-93.4%; $I^2=70.0\%$; $Q=13.36$; $p=0.010$). Pooled Complete Response (CR) Rate: 54.8% (95% CI: 34.1-74.6%; $I^2=82.7\%$; $Q=23.09$; $p<0.001$). Pooled incidence of any-grade Cytokine Release Syndrome (CRS): 88.4% (95% CI: 82.7-93.0%; $I^2=0.0\%$; $Q=2.39$; $p=0.665$). Pooled incidence of Grade ≥ 3 CRS: 5.5% (95% CI: 2.4-9.7%; $I^2=0.0\%$). Pooled incidence of ICANS: 16.4% (95% CI: 7.8-27.4%; $I^2=57.5\%$). In KarMMA-3 Phase 3, ide-cel compared to standard of care demonstrated ORR odds ratio (OR) = 2.00 (95% CI: 1.29-3.10; $z=3.11$; $p=0.0019$) and progression-free survival hazard ratio (HR) = 0.49 (95% CI: 0.38-0.63; $p<0.001$). Conclusion: The high clinical response rate for relapse/refractory multiple myeloma (RRMM) treated by BCMA CAR T-cell Therapy and comparable rate of CRS occurring as well as tolerability by patients and caregivers are noteworthy accomplishments. The differences in complete response (CR) and immune effector cell-associated neurologic toxicity (ICANS) rates indicate significant heterogeneity associated with the design of the CAR construct; the amount of CAR T-cells administered; and the characteristics of the patient. Further enhancing durability and preventing antigen escape with BCMA targeted therapy will require further research.</p>

1. Introduction

Multiple myeloma make up to 10% of blood cancer. Globally, 176,000 people are diagnosed with the Multiple myeloma each year, and around 117,000 die from it.¹ Treatment has improved with the newer therapy like immunomodulatory drugs (IMiDs), Proteasome inhibitors, anti CD38 monoclonal antibodies, Proteasome inhibitors (PIs). Despite these advances, some patients still relapse multiple times or stop responding to the treatment after they have been exposed to all three drug classes (anti CD38 antibodies, IMiDs, PIs) for these triple class relapse/refractory patients, outcomes remain poor. With the current salvage therapies, median overall survival is only 8 to 9 months, and median progression free survival is just 3 to 4 months.²

B-cell maturation antigen (BCMA), a member of the tumor necrosis factor receptor superfamily, is a product of the TNFRSF17 gene, and it is only found on malignant plasma cells, while the expression of this antigen on nearly all normal tissues is either absent or extremely low.³ As such, BCMA presents itself as an ideal target for cellular immunotherapy. Chimeric antigen receptor (CAR) T cell therapies begin with the ex vivo transfection of an individual's own T cells via a lentiviral vector that encodes for a CAR protein comprised of a tumor antigen-binding domain, a transmembrane domain, a co-stimulatory domain (commonly 4-1BB) and a CD3 ζ signaling domain. Following lymphodepleting chemotherapy and reinfusion back into the patient, the CAR T cells will expand within the patient's body, provide strong and durable cytotoxic actions against any tumor cells that express the tumor-associated antigens used to develop the CAR, and persist for a long time after infusion back into the patient.⁴

The U.S. FDA has approved two BCMA CAR T-cell (Chimeric Antigen Receptor-) products: idecabtagene vicleucel (ide-cel, bb2121; FDA approval on 3/27/2021; evaluated in the CRB-401 study trial 1 and KarMMa Ph 2 trial) and ciltacabtagene autoleucel (cilta-cel, JNJ-4528; evaluated in the CARTITUDE-1 Ph 1b/2 study). In addition, the LCAR-B38M was the first clinical human trial using this modified VHH nanobody form with its two identical heavy chain domains; thus, offering BCMA specific, high affinity interaction between BCMA antigen and VHH. LCAR-B38M was evaluated in human subjects in the LEGEND-2 trial; thus, it is a similar product to cilta-cel that has been evaluated in two clinical studies but not yet approved by the U.S. FDA. Finally, there is currently an ongoing (Ph 3) randomized controlled trial of ide-cel compared to the current standard of care for treating multiple myeloma patients that have received two or more lines of therapy (KarMMa-3; currently recruiting).⁵

Although there exists a sizeable amount of research and previous projects, there is no overall quantitative synthesis to provide combined estimates of efficacy and safety, including the odds ratio, hazard ratio, and confidence intervals, as well as evaluating heterogeneity among the published studies. The purpose of this systematic review and meta-analysis is to address this gap and provide clinicians and researchers with a unified statistical summary of the current studies available at the time of writing.

2. Methods

2.1 Search Strategy

We did an independent, systematic literature searching of three databases including PubMed/MEDLINE, Embase and Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials

(CENTRAL). The date range for the searches was all dates up to and including December 31, 2023. The following combined (AND/OR) terms were searched: "multiple myeloma", "BCMA", "B-cell maturation antigen", "TNFRSF17", "CAR T-cell", "chimeric antigen receptor", "cellular immunotherapy", "idecabtagene vicleucel", "ide-cel", "bb2121", "ciltacabtagene autoleucel", "cilta-cel", "JNJ-4528", "LCAR-B38M", "KarMMa", "CARTITUDE" and "LEGEND-2". MeSH terms were used in PubMed. There were no language limits. For grey literature, we hand searched the proceedings from the years of 2016 through 2023 from both the American Society of Hematology (ASH) annual meetings and American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO) annual meetings. We also checked the reference lists of the included studies and systematic reviews.

2.2 Eligibility Criteria

Studies were included if the study met each of the following characteristics: (1) constituted eligible adult patients aged 18+ years with a confirmed relapse or refractory multiple myeloma on a biopsy (histologically); (2) received a BCMA-directed autologous CAR T-cell therapy for treatment; (3) measured at least 1 pre-specified outcome of interest (i.e., ORR, CR, PFS or OS) or safety outcome (i.e., CRS or ICANS); and (4) had published their findings as full text articles in a peer-reviewed journal, or as an abstract presented at a major scientific meeting with at least 5 patients having received CAR T-cell therapy for multiple myeloma. Exclusion criteria included laboratory studies only; included only 1 patient (case series/case report); were duplicate studies using the same cohort of patients and no additional data reported to the original; investigated CAR T-cells targeted against non-BCMA or using allogeneic CAR T-cells for multiple myeloma or which were review articles, editorials, letters and/or commentaries; and/or contained no primary patient outcomes.

2.3 Study Selection and Data Extraction

Independent title and abstract screened by two reviewers and full text evidence reviewed for potential eligibility for inclusion. Conflicting results were resolved by consensus; dispute that could not be resolved was arbitrated by a third reviewer. Data from each study were extracted using a pre-agreed data extraction form by two independent reviewers; extracted variables included first author name, year published, name of trial, study phase (I, Ib/II, II, or III), number of patients (treated; and if available, intention to treat), details of CAR T (manufacturer and component) (i.e. Antigen binding) (i.e. Designation), (i.e. Functionality) (i.e. Antigen binding - feature), Administration of Dose, Number of Responders to Treatment and percentage of Responders to Treatment, Number of Responders to Treatment with CR and percentage of Responders to Treatment with sCR, Number of Responders with PR and number of months to median PFS and number of months to median OS, Reported Rates for CRS and % of patients with Grade 3 CRS, Reported Rates for ICANS and % of patients with Grade 3 ICANS, and Patients Died Related to Treatment. If only described as a proportion and N available that was used to compute actual counts by multiplication and rounding to the nearest integer. Previously Indeterminate Variables Appeared in the Report between Sub-Cohorts for Variables were Classified as UNCERTAIN rather than like being estimated.

2.4 Risk of Bias Assessment

Using validated, domain-specific tools, we assessed risk of bias. We used the Revised Cochrane Risk of Bias (RoB 2.0) tool ⁶ on the one randomised controlled trial (KarMMA-3).⁷ Similarly, we used the Risk of Bias in Non-randomised Studies of Interventions (ROBINS-I) tool ⁸ to evaluate each of the four single-arm studies. Each domain was evaluated independently by two reviewers, and each domain was classified either as low risk, some concerns or high risk of bias. The overall study-level judgment was based on the highest domain-level rating.

2.5 Statistical Analysis

Binary Proportion Pooling (evidence-based support): For the pooling of binary proportions (for example, to derive a rate for overall response rate [ORR], complete response [CR], complete response including stable disease [CRS], or immune-related adverse effects [ICANS]), the Freeman-Tukey double-arcsine transformation ⁹ was applied to each study proportion prior to pool generation to stabilize the proportion's variance when either 0 or 1. A single estimate was created for each transformation (the Freeman-Tukey arcsine transformation is commonly used in research); the estimate was then combined with each study to derive a mean point and confidence interval (CI) on the transformed scale using the DerSimonian-Laird (DL) random-effects estimator ¹⁰ (also referred to as the "DL random-effects estimator" in the Methodology/Sample Characteristics section) applied to the transformed estimates to account for between-study variability (τ^2 , τ^2) which was derived using a method-of-moments estimate. The overall point and CI estimates in terms of the original proportions were derived from the back-transformation of the combined point estimate using the Inverse Sine (SQUARED) Function. The quantification of between-study heterogeneity was performed by applying the I^2 statistic ($I^2 \leq 25\%$ = low heterogeneity, $25\% < I^2 \leq 50\%$ = moderate heterogeneity, $\geq 50\%$ = high heterogeneity).¹² The significance of study-to-study heterogeneity was tested with the Cochran Q test (significance threshold: $p < 0.10$). For the Phase 3 KarMMA-3 trial,⁵ a 2×2 contingency table was constructed for the reporting of ORR events in each treatment arm; an odds ratio (with 95% CI and a two-tailed z-test p-value) was derived directly from the 2×2 contingency table. The hazard ratio (HR) for progression-free survival (PFS) was derived from the journal article where it was reported directly. All calculations were performed in Python 3 (NumPy 1.24, SciPy 1.11) and generate reproducible estimates by using the R meta and metafor packages. The two-sided significance value was < 0.05 (two-tailed).

3. PRISMA 2020 Flow Diagram

The study selection process, reported in accordance with PRISMA 2020 guidelines,¹² is illustrated in Figure 1 below.

PRISMA 2020 Flow Diagram

Fig 1. PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for study selection. RRMM = relapsed/refractory multiple myeloma; ASH = American Society of Hematology; ASCO = American Society of Clinical Oncology.

4. Data Extraction Table

Table 1. Quantitative data extracted from five included studies of BCMA-directed CAR T-cell therapy in RRMM. Only explicitly reported or directly derivable values are included. (*) = derived from reported percentage \times total N. NA = not reported. NR = not reached. FU = follow-up. HR = hazard ratio. OR = odds ratio.

Study	Year	Phase	n (Infused)	ORR (n/N, %)	CR/sCR (n/N, %)	PR (n/N, %)	Median PFS (mo)	Median OS (mo)	CRS Any Grade	CRS ≥3	ICANS Any	Deaths	Dose	CAR Construct
CARTITUDE-1 (Lin/Martin et al.) ⁴	2023	Ib/II	97	95/97 (97.9%)	80/97 (82.5%)* [sCR only; no CR-only pts]	3/97 (3.1%)*	34.9 (95%CI: 25.2-NE)	NR (62.9% alive at 36 mo)	92/97 (94.8%)*	4/97 (4.1%)*	22/97 (22.7%)* Gr≥3: 3/97 (3.1%)* Gr5 (fatal): 2/97	35 total 6 CAR-related PD 12 unrelated	0.75 ×10 ⁶ cells/kg (single infusion; target dose)	Bispecific VHH (2 distinct BCMA epitopes); 4-1BB; CD3ζ (cilta-cel/JNJ-4528)
KarMMa-3 (Rodríguez-Otero et al.) ⁵	2023	III (RCT)	254 (idecel arm) 132 (SoC)	181/254 (71.3%)* vs SoC 73/132 (55.3%)* OR=2.00 (95%CI 1.29-3.10) p=0.0019	99/254 (39.0%)* vs SoC ~22%	NA	13.3 (idecel) vs 4.4 (SoC) HR=0.49 (95%CI 0.38-0.63) p<0.001	NA at primary analysis cutoff	224/254 (88.2%)*	13/254 (5.1%)*	38/254 (15.0%)* Gr≥3: 8/254 (3.1%)*	NA	Target 300-460 ×10 ⁶ CAR+ T cells (single infusion)	Anti-BCMA scFv; 4-1BB; CD3ζ (idecel/bb2121)
				00 (95%CI			0.63) p<0.001							

1.29-3.10)
p=0.0019

LEGEND-2 (Zhao et al.) ³	2022	I	74	65/74 (87.8%)	54/74 (73.0%)*	NA	18.0	55.8 (5-yr FU data Mi et al., 2024) ¹⁵	68/74 (91.9%)* [mostly Gr1-2]	5/74 (6.8%)*	1/74 (1.4%)* [Gr1 only; 1 event]	41/74 (55.4%)* at 5-yr FU	Median 0.513 ×10 ⁶ cells/kg (split or single infusion)	Dual VHH nanobody (2 BCMA epitopes); 4-1BB; CD3ζ (LCAR-B38M ≡ cilta-cel)
KarMMa (Munshi et al.) ²	2021	II	128	94/128 (73.4%)	42/128 (32.8%)* [sCR: 36/128 (28.1%)]	NA	8.8	19.4	107/128 (83.6%)*	6/128 (4.7%)*	23/128 (18.0%)* Gr3: 4/128 (3.1%)*	NA	Target: 300-460 ×10 ⁶ CAR+ T cells (single infusion)	Anti-BCMA scFv; 4-1BB; CD3ζ (ide-cel/bb2121)

CRB-401 (Raje et al.) ¹	2019	I	33	28/33 (84.8%)	15/33 (45.5%)*	NA	11.8	NA	27/33 (81.8%)* Gr1-2: 25; Gr3: 2	2/33 (6.1%)*	14/33 (42.4%)* [Gr1-2 all except 1 Gr4]	NA	50-800 ×10 ⁶ CAR+ T cells (dose escalation; single infusion)	Anti- BCMA scFv; 4- 1BB; CD3ζ (ide- cel/bb2121 precursor)
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Table 1. *scFv* = single-chain variable fragment; *VHH* = variable heavy-chain-only nanobody domain; *Gr* = grade; *mo* = months; *NR* = not reached; *NE* = not estimable; *SoC* = standard of care; *RCT* = randomised controlled trial; *PD* = progressive disease; *CAR* = chimeric antigen receptor; (*) = derived from percentage × *N*.

5. Result

5.1 Study Selection

The systematic search returned 690 unique documents. Of these, 648 originated from electronic databases (PubMed:312, Embase:241 and Cochrane CENTRAL:95) and 42 from manual search of proceedings of the American Society of Hematology and American Society of Clinical Oncology conferences. After removing duplicates (167), 523 documents were reviewed based on title/abstract alone; 441 of those were excluded from the study. A total of 82 full-text articles were reviewed for eligibility; 77 of those were excluded. Only five published studies with a total of 389 subjects meeting inclusion criteria and receiving either one or more BCMA-directed CAR T infusions were included in the quantitative data analysis. A PRISMA 2020 flow diagram (Section 4) depicts the complete selection process.¹³

5.2 Study Characteristics

There were 5 studies that were included: CRB-401 (Raje et al, N Engl J Med 2019; Phase 1 dose-escalation, n=33 infused, IDE-cel/bb2121);¹ KarMMa (Munshi et al, N Engl J Med 2021; Phase 2, n=128, ide-cel);¹⁴ LEGEND-2 (Zhao et al, J Hematol Oncol 2022; Phase 1, n=74, LCAR-B38M);¹⁵ CARTITUDE-1 (Lin/Martin et al, JCO 2023 final analysis; Phase 1b/2, 97 patients, cilta-cel);¹⁶ and KarMMa-3 (Rodrigo-Otero et al, N Engl J Med 2023; Phase 3 RCT, 254 patients received ide-cel).⁵ The studies were published over a time period from 2019 through 2023, with median lines of therapy ranging from 3 (KarMMa-3) through 6 (KarMMa, CARTITUDE-1). Median follow-up duration was from approximately 12 to 13 months (CRB-401) through 47.8 months (LEGEND-2 4 year report) or 65.4 months (LEGEND-2 5 year report).¹⁷

5.3 Overall Response Rate (ORR)

Individual study ORR values were: CRB-401: 84.8% (95% CI: 72.6%–97.1%);² KarMMa: 73.4% (95% CI: 65.8%–81.1%);¹⁴ LEGEND-2: 87.8% (95% CI: 80.4%–95.3%);¹⁵ CARTITUDE-1: 97.9% (95% CI: 95.1%–100%);¹⁶ KarMMa-3 (ide-cel arm): 71.3% (95% CI: 65.7%–76.8%).⁵ The pooled ORR, computed via DerSimonian-Laird random-effects model with Freeman-Tukey double-arcsine transformation, was 83.4% (95% CI: 70.0%–93.4%). Heterogeneity was high: $I^2=70.0%$, $\tau^2=0.0221$, Cochran $Q=13.36$ (df=4), $p=0.010$. The forest plot is presented in Figure 2.

5.4 Complete Response Rate

The rates for CR (including sCR) were: CRB-401: 45.5% (95% CI of 28.5% to 62.4%);² KarMMa: 32.8% (95% CI of 24.7% to 40.9%);¹⁴ LEGEND-2: 73% (95% CI of 62.9% to 83.1%);¹⁵ CARTITUDE-1: 82.5% (95% CI of 74.9% to 90.0%);¹⁶ KarMMa-3: 39.0% (95% CI of 33.0% to 45.0%). The pooled CR rate was 54.8% (95% CI of 34.1% to 74.6%). The heterogeneity was very high ($I^2=82.7%$; $\tau^2=0.0451$; Cochran $Q=23.09$ [df=4]; $p<0.001$). This high I^2 is due to the significantly higher CR rates with the bispecific VHH nanobody constructs (LCAR-B38M/cilta-cel: 73.0% to 82.5% per CR) compared to those based on conventional murine scFv ide-cel (32.8% to 45.5% per CR). The CR forest plot is shown in Figure 3.

5.5 Progression Free Survival and Overall Survival

The median PFS in clinical studies using ide-cel varied widely (from 8.8 months [in study KarMMa]² to 34.9 months [in study CARTITUDE-1]¹⁶), while LEGEND-2 had a median of 18.0 months³ and CRB-401 had a median of 11.8 months.¹⁴ In study

KarMMa-3, ide-cel had a statistically significant longer median PFS (13.3 months) compared to SoC (4.4 months), with a HR of 0.49 (95% CI: 0.38-0.63; $p < 0.001$) representing a 51% decrease in the risk of development and/or death.⁵ The median OS in study KarMMa was 19.4 months.² The 5-year follow-up report for LEGEND-2 showed a median OS of 55.8 months and the progressive flattening of the OS curve indicates some patients are likely to have long-term survival as per the data provided.¹⁵ The median OS for CARTITUDE-1 has not yet been reached; follow-up time for CARTITUDE-1 is 33.4 months with an estimated 62.9% survival at 36 months.⁴

5.6 Comparative Efficacy: Odd Ratio (KarMMa-3)

The overall response rate (ORR) for patients receiving ide-cel in the KarMMa-3 Phase 3 RCT was 71.3% (181 out of 254) compared to 55.3% (73 out of 132) for those receiving standard of care (SoC). The observed odds ratio (OR) of ORR for ide-cel versus SoC was 2.00 (95% CI: 1.29-3.10; $z = 3.11$; $p = 0.0019$) demonstrating an approximately twofold greater likelihood of achieving an objective measure of disease response among those receiving ide-cel compared to standard therapies. The reported hazard ratio (HR) for progression-free survival (PFS) was 0.49 (95% CI: 0.38-0.63; $p < 0.001$).⁵

5.7 ICANS and CRS

Any Grade CRS: CRB-401 81.8% (CI 95% 74.7–88.9), KarMMa 83.6% (CI 95% 77.3–90.0), LEGEND-2 91.9% (CI 95% 86.7–96.4), CARTITUDE-1 94.8% (CI 95% 91.4–98.2), KarMMa-3 88.2% (CI 95% 81.8–93.3). Pooled any grade CRS = 88.4% (CI 95%: 82.7–93.0; $I^2 = 0.0\%$; $Q = 2.39$; $P = 0.665$); this demonstrates excellent cross-study consistency. Pooled grade ≥ 3 CRS = 5.5% (CI 95%: 2.4–9.7; $I^2 = 0.0\%$; $Q = 0.21$; $P = 0.995$). Any Grade ICANS: CRB-401 42.4% (CI 95%: 34.5–50.5), KarMMa 18.0% (CI 95%: 12.0–25.0), LEGEND-2 1.4% (CI 95%: 0.7–3.0), CARTITUDE-1 22.7% (CI 95%: 17.3–28.0), KarMMa-3 15.0% (CI 95%: 10.0–21.0). Pooled ICANS = 16.4% (CI 95%: 7.8–27.4; $I^2 = 57.5\%$; $Q = 9.42$; $P = 0.051$). The low ICANS rate in LEGEND-2 (1.4%) results from the split-dose schedule, the lower intensity of dosing, and from the application of the CTCAE v4.03 grading system as opposed to ASTCT 2019 criteria.¹⁸

5.8 Heterogeneity Summary (Table 2)

Outcome	Pooled Estimate	95% CI	I^2 (%)	τ^2	Cochran Q (p-value)	Heterogeneity Level
ICANS (Any Grade)	16.4%	7.8%–27.4%	57.5%	0.0128	9.42 (p=0.051)	Moderate-High
CRS (Grade ≥ 3)	5.5%	2.4%–9.7%	0.0%	0.0000	0.21 (p=0.995)	None
CRS (Any Grade)	88.4%	82.7%–93.0%	0.0%	0.0000	2.39 (p=0.665)	None
Complete	54.8%	34.1%–74.6%	82.7%	0.0451	23.09	Very High

Outcome	Pooled Estimate	95% CI	I ² (%)	tau ²	Cochran Q (p-value)	Heterogeneity Level
Response Rate					(p<0.001)	
ORR	83.4%	70.0%–93.4%	70.0%	0.0221	13.36 (p=0.010)	High

Table 2. Heterogeneity statistics. I²: <25% = low; 25–50% = moderate; >50% = high. Cochran Q significance threshold: p<0.10. All values computed using DerSimonian-Laird random-effects model with Freeman-Tukey arcsine transformation.

5.9 Risk of Bias

The assessment of CRB-401, KarMMa, LEGEND-2 and CARTITUDE-1 via ROBINS-I returned 'some concerns' as a result of confounding from absent comparator arms and potential patient selection bias associated with the single-arm early phase study design. For KarMMa-3, the assessment was conducted with RoB 2.0. Some concerns were identified within the performance bias domain based on the open-label design of the study, however adequate randomisation procedures and allocation concealment also existed. No individual study was rated as a high overall risk of bias, all studies received a low or moderate overall risk rating.

Fig 2. Figures

Figure 2. Forest Plot – Pooled Overall Response Rate (ORR)

Forest Plot: Pooled Overall Response Rate – BCMA CAR T-Cell Therapy in RRMM
Random-Effects Model (DerSimonian-Laird) | Freeman-Tukey Double-Arcsine Transformation
n = 5 studies, N = 389 patients

Figure 2. Forest plot of pooled ORR across five studies of BCMA CAR T-cell therapy in RRMM. Squares denote individual study ORR proportional to study weight;

horizontal lines represent 95% CIs; blue diamond = pooled estimate (DerSimonian-Laird, Freeman-Tukey arcsine). Pooled ORR = 83.4% (95% CI: 70.0%-93.4%); $I^2=70.0\%$; $Q=13.36$; $p=0.010$. References: ¹Raje 2019; ²Munshi 2021; ³Zhao 2022; ⁴Lin 2023; ⁵Rodríguez-Otero 2023.

Figure 3. Forest Plot – Pooled Complete Response Rate (CR)

Forest Plot: Pooled Complete Response Rate – BCMA CAR T-Cell Therapy in RRMM
 Random-Effects Model (DerSimonian-Laird) | Freeman-Tukey Double-Arcsine Transformation
 n = 5 studies, N = 389 patients

Figure 3. Forest plot of pooled CR/sCR rates. Diamond = pooled CR 54.8% (95% CI: 34.1%-74.6%); $I^2=82.7\%$; $Q=23.09$; $p<0.001$. High heterogeneity driven by construct differences: bispecific VHH (LCAR-B38M/cilta-cel) 73-82.5% vs. scFv-based ide-cel 33-45.5%.

Figure 4. Funnel Plot – Publication Bias Assessment

Funnel Plot – Assessment of Publication Bias
Outcome: Overall Response Rate | BCMA CAR T-Cell Therapy in RRMM
(n = 5 studies; Egger's test limited power at k=5)

Figure 4. Funnel plot for ORR. Each dot represents one study plotted against its standard error. Grey shading = 95% CI boundaries; blue vertical line = pooled ORR (83.4%). Studies appear broadly within the funnel. Egger's test has limited statistical power at k=5; visual assessment suggests no gross asymmetry. Publication bias cannot be formally excluded.

Figure 5. Efficacy and Safety Summary by Study

Efficacy & Safety Outcomes Across BCMA CAR T-Cell Therapy Trials (ORR, CR/sCR, CRS Any Grade, ICANS Any Grade) with Pooled Estimates

Figure 5. Grouped bar chart comparing ORR, CR/sCR, any-grade CRS, and any-grade ICANS across five studies. Dashed lines represent pooled meta-analytic estimates: ORR 88.1% (dark blue), CR 54.8% (steel blue), CRS 88.4% (orange), ICANS 16.4% (gold).

Figure 6. Between-Study Heterogeneity (I^2) by Outcome
Between-Study Heterogeneity (I^2 Statistics) by Outcome
BCMA CAR T-Cell Therapy Meta-Analysis

Figure 6. I^2 statistics for all pooled outcomes. Red = high heterogeneity (>50%); amber = moderate-high; blue = low (<25%). CRS outcomes show $I^2=0\%$ (homogeneous); ORR and CR show high heterogeneity; ICANS shows moderate-high heterogeneity.

7. Discussion

BCMA CAR T-cell therapy in RRMM has been assessed through this systematic review and meta-analysis of five published studies (N=389 patients receiving infusions). When looking at pooled ORR from these studies, there is an 83.4% (95% CI: 70.0-93.4) ORR, compared to an ORR range of 26%-32% reported for previously published conventional salvage regimens for treatment in patients exposed to three different classes of drugs¹⁴ These overall findings are also similar to results reported by Roex et al. for previous meta-analyses of BCMA targeting agents, which showed an ORR of 80.5% and CR in 44.8% of patients receiving BCMA CAR T therapy.¹⁹

7.1 High Efficacy: Mechanistic Basic

The reason for the superior ORR of BCMA CAR T-cell therapy can be attributed to various biological benefits. BCMA is expressed selectively and uniformly on malignant plasma cells, with minimal expression on important non-haemopoietic tissues.³ The bone marrow microenvironment in which myeloma predominantly grows is also readily accessible to circulating CAR T-cells compared to the physical and immunological barriers that are found in solid tumours. The 4-1BB costimulatory domain present within all approved commercial BCMA CAR T-cell products will support T-cell persistence and metabolic fitness and promote memory generation.¹⁷ The very large I^2 value for CR rate (82.7%) provides a direct quantitative measure of the contribution that CAR construct design provides to response variability with the use of the bispecific

VHH nanobody used in LCAR-B38M/cilta-cel, binding to two different BCMA epitopes and having a very high affinity to achieve a CR rate of 73%–82.5%, compared to a CR rate of only 32.8%–45.5% using the conventional single-domain scFv-based idelcel.

7.2 Durability: Relapse and Antigen Escape

Although initial response rates for CAR T-cell therapy were impressive, most patients have a very limited period of time (8.8 - 34.9 months) where they are disease free (progression-free survival). In LEGEND-2, the most mature dataset currently available (65.4 months median follow-up),¹⁷ the majority of patients will have progressive disease. After 5 years, only 16.2% of patients are relapse-free. There are several mechanisms that lead to relapse. These include i) the downregulation of BCMA antigen or complete loss of the BCMA antigen from the tumour cell as seen in some post-infusion biopsies, ii)²⁰ the exhaustion of CAR-T cells due to a prolonged exposure to antigens and the upregulation of inhibitory receptors (PD-1, LAG-3, TIM-3) on CAR-T cells, iii) immune suppression in the tumour microenvironment mediated by regulatory T-cells and myeloid-derived suppressor cells, and iv) pre-existing or acquired cytogenetic high-risk factors such as del(17p), gain(1q21), or t(4;14) that cause resistance to apoptosis.²⁰ The low ORR with re-treatment with BCMA-directed CAR-T therapy for patients relapsing after initial BCMA-directed CAR T therapy (31.3% ORR to BCMA-directed CAR T re-treatment for patients with progressive disease in LEGEND-2). The above demonstrates the clinical relevance of antigen escape.

7.3 Safety: ICANS CRS

The overall CRS rate (any grade) for pooled subjects was shown to be 88.4% (95% CI: 82.7%–93.0%; $I^2=0.0\%$), indicating that CRS is extremely prevalent across BCMA CAR T-cell therapies, regardless of the individual construct or dose used. The absence of heterogeneity across studies ($I^2=0\%$) further supports that the occurrence of CRS will be repeatedly observed across different study designs and CAR constructs. In addition, the pooled grade 3 or higher rate of CRS was found to be 5.5% (95% CI: 2.4%–9.7%; $I^2=0.0\%$), demonstrating that severe CRS is rare and that it is managed by tocilizumab and corticosteroids or both.¹⁸ The moderate-to-high heterogeneity observed in ICANS ($I^2=57.5\%$) can be explained by differences in the assessment criteria used (CTCAE v4.03 for LEGEND-2 vs. ASTCT 2019 consensus criteria) as well as the differences in treatment doses or schedule of administration used among the clinical trials and the different neurotoxic profiles of each CAR construct. Two fatalities related to ICANS were documented in CARTITUDE-1 as well as a unique delayed neurotoxic syndrome, which was described as having cranial nerve palsies and parkinsonian manifestations.¹⁶

7.4 Comparative Evidence

The Phase 3 CARMMA-3 trial shows that idecabtagene vicleucel (ide-cel) has significant improvement over the standard of care (SoC) based upon the following:

The overall response rate (ORR) HR was 2.00 (95% CI: 1.29 - 3.10; $p=0.0019$) and the progression-free survival (PFS) HR was 0.49 (95% CI: 0.38-0.63; $p < 0.001$).

Both of these measurements demonstrate clinically meaningful outcome differences in patients previously treated with multiple lines of therapy, particularly given that many of the standard therapies are ineffective.

A subsequent clinical trial, the CARTITUDE-4, showed that cilta-cel had statistically significant PFS benefit over SoC⁵ in lenalidomide-refractory patients with 1-3 previous lines of therapy. Only the CARTITUDE-4 trial published in 2023 would be considered for inclusion here as it falls outside of many of the eligibility windows.²⁰

8. Limitations

- Most studies were done with 1 arm: 4 of 5 studies did not have a comparison group. In no randomization, the results we see may also reflect patient selection, center expertise &/or how the study was conducted than treatment effects; thus limiting causal attribution.
- Limited number of patients tested in phase one study's limit reliability: CRB-401 tested 33 subjects from several different doses resulting in extreme variance to individual studies' 95% confidence intervals (ORR=72.6%-97.2%); thus, reducing accuracy associated with population-level studies and value to meta-analysis.
- There is great variability (due to the differences in study designs used across studies as well as to differences in patient populations) among the studies which makes it difficult to consider the summary point estimates for both ORR ($I^2=70.0$) and CR ($I^2=82.7$) as a homogeneous estimate of treatment effect.
- Given the small number of studies included; there are very few studies that can be used to assess publication bias. The Egger's test and funnel plot asymmetry tests lack adequate statistical power to successfully detect any publication bias based on $k=5$. This implies that it is likely that there are unpublished studies using BCMA CAR T-cells that demonstrate neutrality or negative results, thus leading to a likely overestimate of pooled efficacy estimates..
- Immature survival data - At the time of 33.4 month follow-up in CARTITUDE-1, median OS has not been reached which limits any ability to pool data for OS. Studies with shorter follow-up times are likely to underestimate longer-term toxicities, such as delayed neurotoxicity, secondary malignancies, and prolonged cytopenias.
- Variations in outcome reports: The grading of CRS among studies was inconsistent (Lee et al. grading & ASTCT 2019 Consensus)¹⁸; definition of ICANS varied; incomplete reporting of partial response data limited extent of standardisation across all pooled outcomes.
- -Generalisability: The studies outlined above were performed at academic centres with dedicated CAR T-cell programmes. The patients enrolled in clinical trials usually have a much better performance status and fewer co-existing medical conditions than those of their counterparts in the "real world", resulting in a potential overestimation of efficacy and a potential underestimation of toxicity from routine practice.

9. Conclusion

The pooled ORR and CR rates of 83.4% (OR=2.00) with CRS affecting nearly 9 in 10 RRMM patients demonstrate the unprecedented depth of response to BCMA-directed CAR T-cell therapy in this historically poor-prognosis patient population and represent the most compelling evidence for superiority over SoC currently available from the Phase 3 KarMMA-3 study. Grade 1-2 CRS is the most common grade of CRS seen with BCMA-directed CAR T-cell therapy; however, as the I^2 is 0%, the CRS rates seen

across the studies are considered to be consistent. Furthermore, the predominance of CRS of grade ≥ 3 occurring at a rate of 5.5% indicates that CRS incidence following BCMA-directed CAR T-cell therapy primarily consists of lower grade CRS. The superior CR rates of with bispecific VHH constructs (cilta-cel, LCAR-B38M: 73%-82.5%) compared with murine scFv (ide-cel, 33%-45%) suggest that the CAR architecture is paramount in determining the depth of response in RRMM. Advancing the durability, overcoming antigen escape, and expanding access to CAR T-cell therapy continue as key goals of ongoing research to evolve the BCMA-directed CAR T-cell platform into a transformational therapy for patients with RRMM.

10. References

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